

SALMONELLA NECK ABSCESS IN A DIABETIC MALE***¹Dr. Gargi Bhattacharya, ²Dr. Moinak Basu, ³Dr. Subhrajit Das**

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ABSTRACT

We present a case of a young diabetic male presenting with a neck swelling. Imaging studies revealed an abscess in the neck. Salmonella Enteritidis was isolated from the aspirate and he was treated with incision and drainage along with oral antibiotics. Interestingly, the patient provided history of similar clinical presentations in a number of the residents of his native village which offers a novel scenario. Literature review revealed diabetes as an important predisposing factor for focal Non Typhoidal Salmonella manifestations. Hence it is prudent to consider Salmonella as a causative agent of focal abscesses especially in immune compromised hosts.

KEYWORDS: Neck abscess, Diabetes mellitus, Non Typhoid Salmonella.

1. INTRODUCTION

Salmonella is an important and widely prevalent human pathogen affecting all age groups. In the genus Salmonella,

Salmonella Enterica is the Type species and majority of the human pathogens belong to this subspecies including Salmonella Typhi.^[1] Salmonella Typhi and Paratyphi are characteristically called Typhoidal Salmonella as they are most commonly associated with Typhoid fever. The other sub species are referred to as non Typhoidal Salmonella (NTS) that primarily cause self limiting gastroenteritis. Extra Intestinal manifestations including blood stream infections as a result of NTS are prevalent in people with lowered immunity. Here we present a case of neck abscess caused by Non Typhoidal Salmonella in a young diabetic male.

2. CASE HISTORY

A 34 year old male patient presented to the ENT out-patient department with a swelling in the left side of the neck since 15 days and fever for the last 7 days. He was diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus 4 years ago and was on Tab Gliclazide XR 60. No other significant past history was noted. There was no history of any trauma, dental or oral procedure or similar episodes in the past.

On general examination, the patient was found to be febrile and had tachycardia. Pallor, jaundice, cyanosis and oedema were absent. Local examination revealed an erythematous, tender cystic swelling on the left antero-lateral aspect of the neck with congested oropharynx. There were no remarkable systemic findings.

All the relevant investigations were sent including USG and USG guided FNAC from the neck swelling. His blood picture showed neutrophilic leucocytosis (13300 with 81% neutrophils). USG of the neck demonstrated an abscess in the left anterolateral aspect of neck extending into the submandibular gland, anterior aspect of carotid space, medial sternothyroid, sternocleidomastoid and anterior platysma muscles (Figure_1). A radiological diagnosis of sternocleidomastoid abscess was given; incision and drainage was planned.

Empiric treatment was initiated with IV amoxicillin clavulanic acid and metronidazole every 8 hourly. The aspirate from the abscess was purulent and mixed with blood. It was sent for Gram stain, bacterial culture and sensitivity, AFB stain and Genexpert for Mycobacterium tuberculosis. In addition, 2 sets of blood cultures were also drawn.

AFB stain and Genexpert for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* came back negative. FNAC of the aspirate showed necrotising inflammation with suppuration. Gram stain demonstrated

presence of Gram negative bacilli and pus cells. Interestingly culture from the aspirate showed growth of Non lactose fermenting colonies on MacConkey's agar and non haemolytic colonies on Blood agar after overnight incubation. The isolate was analysed in Vitek2 and gave an excellent identification (99%) of Salmonella group. As the findings were unanticipated - the isolate was re-analysed and produced the same results. The isolate was further identified as Salmonella Enterica subspecies enterica serovar Enteritidis (Poly A-S+Vi positive, OMA positive, O9 positive, H-g positive and H-m positive).

The isolate was susceptible to ceftriaxone, azithromycin and cotrimoxazole and showed intermediate sensitivity to ciprofloxacin. Incision and drainage of the abscess was performed under USG guidance and patient was started on cotrimoxazole. He was discharged with cotrimoxazole, oral hypoglycaemic (teneligliptin) and insulin. His blood cultures came back negative for any growth.

On follow up in the medicine and ENT OPD after 2 weeks, his neck swelling did not show any signs of recurrence and had entirely healed. We obtained a history from the patient for a second time to find out if he had suffered from Enteric fever in the recent past. Although there was no such history, he had visited his village where some of the villagers also had similar swellings in the neck which subsided on its own as per the patient's account. He gave history of occasional street food consumption and drinking unfiltered tube-well water.

Table 1: Summary of literature review.

Author/year	Patient	Manifestation	Systemic symptoms	Diabetes	Blood picture	Recurrence	Species
Sivakumar S et al,2022 ^[8]	60 M	Painful swelling right side of neck	Low grade fever	Yes	Neutrophillic leucocytosis (13900)	No	Salmonella sp. Non typhoidal
Sugimoto R et al, 2017 ^[9]	26 M	Left-sided neck swelling	Nil	Yes	Neutrophillic leucocytosis (13100)	Yes	S. Choleraesuis
Pastagia M et al, 2013 ^[5]	54 M	Para pharyngeal abscess	Nil	Yes	Not mentioned	no	S. Typhimurium
Doya et al, 2022 ^[10]	7 F	Painful swelling right side of neck	Fever (Widalpos)	No	Neutrophillic leucocytosis (40000)	No	S Typhi
Behera et al, 2012 ^[11]	22 M	Painful swelling right side of neck	Fever	No	Neutrophillic leucocytosis (13000)	Yes	S paratyphi
Jayasundara	43 M	left-sided neck	Fever,	Yes	Neutrophillic	No	S Enteritidis

et al, 2021 ^[12]		swelling	diarrhoea (1 month back)		leucocytosis (19000)		
Kwon et al, 2008 ^[13]	67 F	Painful swelling right side of neck	Fever	Yes (also cirrhosis of liver)	Leucocytosis (86%) with normal counts	No	<i>Salmonella</i> serotype D

Table 1: The table highlights the important features of similar cases reviewed.

Figure 1: USG picture showing neck abscess.

USG picture shows an abscess of 8.44X8.81X4.36 cu cm containing 169.69 mL of fluid.

3. DISCUSSION

Neck abscess is usually caused by organisms like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus sp.*, *Klebsiella sp.*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Salmonella* causing neck abscess is very uncommon, with an incidence of less than 1%.^[2]

The common clinical manifestation of infections caused by non-Typhoidal *Salmonella* serotypes (NTS) like Enteritidis and Typhimurium is gastroenteritis associated with consumption of contaminated poultry. However in children and immune-compromised hosts NTS can cause septicemia and invasive infections with high mortality.^[1] Extra intestinal sites of infection include- urinary tract, respiratory tract, osteoarticular, hepatic or splenic abscess, lymph nodes and vascular structures.^[3,4,14]

The bacteria can survive for unknown periods of time in macrophages and distal infection sites can present long after an acute gastrointestinal illness.^[5] The cause of abscess formation

is hypothesized either by direct spread of the bacteria from the oropharyngeal space to the lymph nodes or more likely hematogenous seeding of the nodes.^[6]

The majority of the cases of extraintestinal infection with NTS occur in patients with certain predisposing factors like HIV, Diabetes mellitus, malignancy, chronic lung diseases or immune suppressive therapy.^[7] Diabetes mellitus, by reducing the gastric acidity level and the transit time concomitantly makes the environment favourable for harbouring Salmonella.

A summary of the results of literature search for Salmonella neck abscess is presented in Table_1.

Some of the common features of the Salmonella neck abscess are dearth of systemic signs and symptoms apart from fever and Neutrophilic leucocytosis (<20000). Diabetes mellitus is a regular attribute in the reported cases. Interestingly the cases where lesion was caused by Typhoidal Salmonella, Diabetes mellitus was not reported as a predisposing factor.

Unfortunately here we could not substantiate the history given by the patient about similar cases in his native village nonetheless it certainly presents an exceptional picture. Some questions that crop up are whether the suspected cases were also immune-compromised, or if the lesions healed spontaneously or were administered antibiotics without an attempt at diagnosis.

We must consider Salmonella as a causative factor in focal abscesses in immune-compromised patients. Reversibly, if we find Salmonella as a causative agent of any abscess, an underlying immune compromising status should be explored.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no conflict of interest or funding sources.

Consent

Informed consent has been obtained from the patient.

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